

Early Failure Detection in Secondary Cryogenic Pumps through Machine Learning Techniques in the Context of Industry 4.0

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Abstract

The paper presents a new approach to Asset Management that utilizes Industry 4.0 techniques and Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically Machine Learning (ML). The research emphasizes early anomaly detection and failure mode classification in operating equipment in dynamic ranges.

The study is based on the secondary cryogenic pumps of a Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) regasification plant, which operate in a highly dynamic environment with rapid changes in pressure. Traditional condition monitoring methods, which rely on monitoring operational parameters and physical measurements, are contrasted with the proposed ML-based approach. ML models aim to detect early-stage issues and forecast critical failures by exploiting complex and nonlinear relationships among multiple operational variables. For the study, six years of historical data gathered by the different sensors of the 4 pumps have been used.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Failure Mode Classification; Cryogenic Equipment; Prognosis; Diagnosis

1. Introduction

Enagás is a leading Spanish company in natural gas (NG) transportation, contributing to the development of the Spanish Gas System, recognized for its safety and diversified supply. The company faces the challenge of ensuring the proper operation of all its assets, including secondary pumps, essential for the regasification process of LNG, which operate in cryogenic conditions, adding complexity and risk of failures (figure 1). Therefore, it is important to monitor their operation regularly to detect possible anomalies (Collart et al., 2022).

The purpose of this research is to develop a tool that can identify secondary pumps with anomalous operation before incidents occur (Dutta et al., 2021). Additionally, the study aims to address key questions about the parameters and patterns associated with the normal operation of these pumps.

However, the study has limitations due to the fact that it was conducted on a limited number of Enagás pumps, which may affect the generalization of the results to all cryogenic secondary pumps. Additionally, the study is focused on a limited number of operating parameters, there is the possibility that there are other unidentified normal patterns (Fuente et al., 2020).

Figure 1: LNG Regasification Process

2. Literature Review

The study at Enagás focuses to enhance the efficiency and predictive maintenance of cryogenic pumps using advanced ML and deep learning (DL) techniques within the industry 4.0 framework. This involves real-time data collection and analysis from Enagás' SCADA system to identify patterns and anomalies, predicting failures and improving preventive maintenance. Recent research highlights the effectiveness of transfer learning and meta-learning models in improving anomaly detection accuracy in cryogenic pumps, offering faster and more efficient solutions (Fengqian et al., 2022).

Cryogenic pumps are crucial in the LNG industry due to their ability to handle fluids at extremely low temperatures. The literature emphasizes their specialized design and the challenges in their operation and maintenance, particularly the importance of reliability and energy efficiency (Cui et al., 2024). Significant challenges in maintaining cryogenic pumps include mechanical wear and adverse operating conditions, which affect performance and longevity (Adumene et al., 2023). Energy efficiency is also critical, as optimal design and operation can lead to significant energy savings.

The SCADA system at Enagás provides a robust platform for real-time data collection from cryogenic pumps, including variables such as pressure, temperature, flow, and vibration, which are crucial for predictive analysis. Integrating SCADA data with ML techniques enhances early fault detection and reduces downtime (Ehu, 2021; Fernandes et al., 2022).

DL techniques, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), have shown promising results in fault prediction for cryogenic pumps by analyzing time series data and identifying complex patterns (Hewamalage et al., 2020; Zhang & Li, 2021). These techniques improve early fault detection and optimize predictive maintenance.

Viswanathan et al. (2023) suggest that ML-based anomaly detection can enhance industrial pumps, including cryogenic ones, by identifying issues early. Studies comparing ML techniques for fault prediction in LNG pumps at regasification plants show these models outperform traditional methods in accuracy and efficiency.

Moreover, Implementing ML models for the predictive maintenance of cryogenic pumps can help reduce operational and maintenance costs, improve energy efficiency, and extend equipment lifespan. This is primarily due to these models' ability to identify failures before they become critical issues, thereby avoiding unplanned downtime and costly maintenance interventions (Achouch et al., 2022).

Finally, tools like RapidMiner (RM) have also been identified as essential for applying ML and real-time data analysis due to their ease of use, versatility, and ability to integrate with SCADA systems (Apriade, 2023).

3. Methodology

The methodology employed in the study comprises two major blocks, each designed to address specific aspects of the analysis of Enagás' secondary pumps:

Data Preprocessing:

- Historical operation data of the pumps are collected over a 6-year period, from 2013 to 2020, with a data extraction granularity of one minute.
- This data is sourced from sensors located on the pumps and stored in the PI osisoft (PI) software.
- It is complemented with information on the maintenance history and redesigns of each equipment, vital for determining suitable periods for model training and interpreting production results.

Comparison and Selection of ML Models:

- The RM tool is utilized, previously proven in similar studies, for its versatility and ease of use.
- Different ML models are explored to select the most suitable for the analysis of the secondary pumps' data.

The methodology used in the study consists of three main blocks. The RM tool is used, which has been previously tested in similar studies for its versatility and ease of use (Apriade, 2023).

3.1. Data processing:

The data processing begins with the consolidation of historical PI files to form a coherent and complete database. This data ingestion is carried out using RM Studio.

Files are grouped together; missing data and outliers are removed.

The operational signals collected from PI are:

- Date [dd.mm.aaaa hh:mm:ss]
- Flow rate
- Aspiration Temp
- Discharge Temp
- Operating state
- Operating hours since the last major maintenance
- Total operating hours
- Intensity
- Power
- Aspiration Pressure
- Discharge Pressure
- Pot Level
- Performance
- Number of stars

The process of extraction, chronological sorting, and storage is carried out with the assistance of RM, thus generating a unique database covering the period from 2013 to 2020, with approximately 4 million records.

Data Cleansing involves removing lines without information for any of the signals and identifying and eliminating outliers using boxplot representation and the interquartile range. For instance, in the case of discharge T^a , the lower and upper limits are calculated based on the interquartile range, and any outliers beyond these limits are removed from the study (figure 2).

Example: Discharge Temp

Q1(25%), Lower q. = -128,54°C

Q3 (75%), upper q. = -114,57°C

$L = (Q1 - Q3) = 13,97°C$

Figure 2 – Interpretation of the Box Plot Representation.

Thus, the outliers for the Discharge T^a would be:

- Lower Q1: $-128,54°C - (1,5 \times L) = < -149,50°C$
- Uper Q3: $-114,57 + (1,5 \times L) = > -93,62°C$

3.1.1. Study of Variable Correlation

In the selection of variables to obtain a consistent model that replicates the normal behavior of secondary cryogenic pumps and detects anomalies, a study of the correlation matrix is conducted. Since these pumps are rotating equipment with constant operation, the goal is to identify representative variables capable of discriminating different behaviors based on condition or operating modes.

The correlation matrix is obtained using RM, and variables with 100% correlation with power are discarded.

In the resulting correlation table, variables with less than 100% correlation with power are identified as candidates for the consumed power prediction model (table 1).

Attributes	Flow rate	Aspiration T ^a	Discharge T ^a	Current	Power	Discharge pressure	Pot level	Start count	Aspiration pressure
Flow rate	1	-0.258	-0.277	0.996	0.997	0.985	0.970	-0.076	0.248
Aspiration T^a	-0.258	1	0.986	-0.222	-0.220	-0.334	-0.923	0.278	-0.911
Discharge T^a	-0.277	0.986	1	-0.239	-0.239	-0.349	-0.928	0.252	-0.892
Current	0.996	-0.222	-0.239	1	1.000	0.987	0.970	-0.058	0.205
Power	0.997	-0.220	-0.239	1.000	1	0.990	0.975	-0.012	0.202
Discharge pressure	0.985	-0.334	-0.349	0.987	0.990	1	0.975	-0.099	0.325
Pot level	0.970	-0.923	-0.928	0.970	0.975	0.975	1	-0.209	0.847
Start count	1	-0.258	-0.277	0.996	0.997	0.985	0.970	-0.076	0.248
Aspiration pressure	-0.258	1	0.986	-0.222	-0.220	-0.334	-0.923	0.278	-0.911

Table 1 – Correlation Matrix.

In the following figure (figure 3), the correlation of variables with the pump’s point power is ordered from smallest to largest.

Figure 3 – Graphical representation of the correlation of variables with the pump’s consumed power

These variables are:

- Discharge Pressure
- Pot Level
- Discharge T^a
- Aspiration T^a

- Aspiration Pressure
- Start count --> It is excluded due to the lack of information regarding this variable in many cases.
- Power

The consumed power variable will be used as the target variable because it is closely correlated with flow rate, current, and discharge pressure, which accurately represent the behavior of the operating conditions. As such, it provides a simplified representation of the pump's performance. This approach helps reduce multicollinearity, enhancing the robustness and generalization of the model by avoiding redundancies.

This technique of using power as a target variable in predictive maintenance is commonly applied in the industry due to its strong relationship with other key operational metrics (Zhang & Wang, 2021).

3.2. Comparison and Selection of ML Models

To compare models in RM the steps to follow are: Upload the training data, select the input variables, select the variable to predict, select the algorithms to compare and run and analyze the results.

3.2.1. Comparison of ML algorithms

To compare ML algorithms in predicting the power consumed in secondary cryogenic pumps, RM's Automodel option is used. The algorithms evaluated include Generalized Linear Model, DL, Decision Tree, and Random Forest.

Linear models, such as the Generalized Linear Model (GLM), are known for their simplicity and computational efficiency. These models assume a linear relationship between the input variables and the target variable, making them highly interpretable and quick to train. However, their ability to capture complex relationships in the data is limited, which can result in suboptimal performance in problems where the relationships are nonlinear (Dalatu et al., 2016). Nonlinear models, such as DL and Random Forest, are capable of capturing complex and nonlinear patterns in the data; they can handle more intricate relationships between variables (Giudici et al., 2024).

The results of the comparison*, RM's Automodel, are presented in Table 2. It is observed that the best performance is achieved with the Random Forest and Deep Learning** models, which have a time-efficient performance.

Model	Correlation	Standard desviation	Total time	Training time	scoring time
Generalized linear model	0.998	±0	3 s	2 ms	1 ms
Deep learning	0.999	±0.001	1 min 14 s	495 ms	18 ms
Decision tree	0.999	±0.001	8 s	2 ms	1 ms
Random forest	1	±0	1 min 11 s	110 ms	89 ms

Table 2 – Results of the comparison of the different algorithms.

The choice of model is based on a balance between precision, efficiency, and complexity of the problem. Although Random Forest excels in correlation between real power and prediction power and efficiency, the DL model is chosen due to its high correlation, consistency, ability to capture complex patterns, and its potential for improvement with additional data. The original and more simplified variant of RNNs is chosen (LeCun et al., 2015).

* RM's Automodel uses cross-validation to evaluate the model's accuracy. This process is repeated multiple times, and the results are averaged to obtain a robust estimate of the model's performance. It compares the models using various performance metrics, such as mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

** En RM, Deep Learning is based on a multi-layer feed-forward artificial neural network that is trained with stochastic gradient descent using backpropagation.

3.2.2. Comparing different variants of the RNNs algorithm

The next step consists of a more detailed study of the different variants of the RNN model, for this, different alternatives will be designed and compared to use the most powerful and most accurate in the study.

A custom-tailored process is designed for the secondary pumps, with the purpose of training the model using a portion of the dataset and subsequently deploying it in production with another dataset before the failure recorded in the Maintenance Management System (MMS). However, this is detailed in the following section.

Now the study is focused on analyzing which configuration of the RNN algorithm is most suitable for this use case.

For the initial model, the standard configuration of RM is chosen, and the remaining models will be variations where the hidden layers and neurons are modified. Some notable configurations include RN-7-5-1, RN-7-8-1, RN-7-8-4-1, and RN-7-5-2-1.

Metrics such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), t penalizes larger errors more heavily due to the squaring of errors before averaging; Mean Absolute Error (MAE), this makes it more interpretable as it reflects the average prediction error in a linear fashion; Relative Root Mean Square Error (R-RMSE), expresses the error as a percentage of the actual value, providing a relative view of the error concerning the actual values; and Correlation, measures the strength and direction of the relationship between the model predictions and the actual values. A value closer to 0 suggests no linear relationship between them. These are employed to evaluate the models.

Formula RMSE: $\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$ Where y_i is the actual value and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value.

Formula MAE: $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$ Where y_i is the actual value and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value.

$$\text{Formula MER: } \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{y_i} \times 100$$

Correlation (R): $\frac{\sum((y_i - \bar{y}) \cdot (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}}))}{\sqrt{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2 \cdot \sum(\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})^2}}$ Where \bar{y} and $\bar{\hat{y}}$ are the means of the actual and predicted values, respectively.

The results are presented in Table 3:

Model	RMSE	MAE	MER	Correlation
RN (7- 5-1) default	6,236	4,727 ± 4,067	0,52% ± 0,45%	0,994
RN (7-8-1)	6,337	4,853 ± 4,075	0,53% ± 0,45%	0,994
RN (7-8-4-1)	6,32	4,811 ± 4,098	0,53% ± 0,45%	0,993
RN (7-5-2-1)	6,137	4,719 ± 3,923	0,52% ± 0,43%	0,994
Deep Learning	7,247	5,821 ± 4,315	0,69% ± 0,94%	0,994

Table 3 – Comparing Results of Different Neural Network Architectures for Secondary Pumps.

The RMSE is the most appropriate metric for selecting the best model, as it penalizes larger errors, which is crucial in systems where minimizing prediction failures is essential. The RN-7-5-1 model provides a good balance between simplicity, low error (as indicated by RMSE and MAE), and high correlation, making it the best option. It is decided to continue the study with a neural network having an input layer with 7 neurons, a hidden layer with 5 neurons, and an output layer with 1 neuron, architecture RN-7-5-1, although performance metrics indicate that the RN-7-5-2-1 model would be the best, this model adds complexity to the architecture and increases computational cost, which is considered not to provide a differentiating value to the result (Hodson, 2022).

The chosen neural network architecture for further study consists of the following layers:

- Input layer: 7 neurons, which receive input data corresponding to the number of features.
- Hidden layers: These layers, located between the input and output layers, extract relevant features from the input data. In deep neural networks, there can be multiple hidden layers, each composed of neurons.
- Output layer: 1 neuron, responsible for producing the final model output (Power).

This architecture, denoted as RN-7-5-1, strikes a balance between simplicity, computational efficiency (due to fewer neurons), and the ability to learn complex patterns while controlling model complexity through regularization.

4. Model Training and Validation

A custom-tailored process is designed for the secondary pumps.

This process involves data preparation to validate, train, and test the RNN model with the RN-7-5-1 architecture in two distinct contexts: before and after failure. The temporal subdivision and the validation and testing approach allowed for the evaluation of the model's performance under simulated conditions (before failure) and on future data (both before and after failure), enhancing the model's generalization capability (Crespo et al., 2024).

Different scenarios were defined according to the operational phases of a secondary pump, from startup to the end of its operational life. Five specific scenarios were identified:

- **Equipment started up after a new installation or following major maintenance (E0):** corresponds to the initial hours of operation, during which the equipment is expected to undergo a running-in period to assess its performance. This scenario varies depending on each manufacturer and equipment; in this case, it is considered to be the first 200-300 hours of operation.
- **Equipment as new scenario (E1):** corresponds to the initial hours of operation of the equipment following major maintenance or replacement, approximately constituting 20% of the equipment's total lifespan, around 3,500-4,000 first hours of operation.
- **Normal operation scenario of the equipment (E2):** corresponds to the majority of the equipment's lifespan, between 20% and 80% of the time since startup, i.e., between 4,000 and 16,000 hours of operation.
- **End-of-life operation scenario (E3):** corresponds to the final period, from 80% of the equipment's lifespan until the next major maintenance.
- **Pre-failure operation scenario (E4):** this less common scenario in equipment corresponds to the period before failure, which will depend on each equipment and each failure mode. To analyze the behavior, a temporal window of 3,000 hours of operation prior to the failure will be used.

The following figure (figure 4) depicts a representation of the temporal evolution of the operating hours of a secondary pump, the percentages of time over the total lifespan, the different time periods, and the identification of the scenarios.

Figure 4. Scenarios for the study of behavior patterns with a ML model.

From scenario E1, information is obtained regarding how far the pump's consumption or performance is from ideal behavior. With this idea, this information can be used to assign different risk levels to the different scenarios, as will be seen later. A scenario exhibiting behavior deviating more significantly from the optimal is deemed to possess a higher risk profile (Marti-Puig et al., 2021).

In our analysis, the GA-115-H pump from Huelva is a pump that has not experienced any failures. Specifically, it has passed through scenario E1 and remains in scenario E2.

Graph 1. Absolute Error Plot of a Faultless Pump Over a Specified Time Period

For this pump , **with no detected failure mode**, the Absolute Power Error (EA) [kW] is **less than 15 kW**, and the mean value is **5 kW ± 5 kW** (Graph 1).

A new variable is generated, **Absolute Power Error (AE) [kW]**, which is nothing more than the absolute difference between the actual Power and the Power Prediction at each time instant. This variable will give an idea of how far or close the pump's consumption is from the consumption when it is in a "like-new" state, corresponding to what it would have in an E1 scenario. The characteristic AE of a pump in the different scenarios is:

- **Scenario E1:** The **AE** should be minimal, characterized by having an average value distribution equal to **5 kW ± 5 kW**, and **less than 15 kW**.
- **Scenario E2:** AE behavior similar to E1, where high values will not appear until reaching the end of E2, due to the aging of the pump or premature deterioration.
- **Scenario E3:** The AE begins to accumulate operating hours at higher values, but in a smoothed and sustained manner.
- **Scenario E4:** The AE frequently spikes, in an exponential manner.

5. Results Analysis (prognosis)

5.1. Application to the P-2003-A secondary pump, in Barcelona, in scenarios E2, E3 and E4

From the historical data available for this pump, it is known that a major maintenance was performed, and an inverter was also installed. Shortly after, the failure occurred.

The previous process from Figure 6 is executed, and the behavior of the new AE variable is observed before and after the inverter installation.

Graph 2 shows the behavior of the Absolute Error (AE) of the power before the inverter installation and the major maintenance with 21,099 hours of operation.

Graph 2. Distribution plot of the Absolute Power Error behavior before the inverter installation and major maintenance with 21,099 hours of operation.

The mean value of AE before the major maintenance is 5.5 kW \pm 4 kW with a maximum of 27.1 kW.

Graph 3 shows the behavior of the Absolute Power Error just before the failure on May 8, but after the major maintenance, with 888 hours of operation and 12 starts (E3 and E4).

Graph 3. Distribution plot of the Absolute Power Error behavior just before the failure and after the major maintenance.

The mean value of AE before the failure, but after the major maintenance, is 12.5 kW \pm 12.9 kW with a maximum of 85.1 kW.

It is clearly observed that the Absolute Error behavior before the major maintenance is completely different from before the failure. Before the failure, more minutes accumulate at higher absolute error values, as reflected in the distribution plots of the Absolute Error (Graphs 2 and 3).

5.2. Application to the P-2003-B secondary pump, in Barcelona, in scenarios E2 y E4

From the historical data available for this pump, it is known that the pump degraded until the major maintenance was performed, after which the failure occurred.

The training was conducted with data available from the period ranging from 13,000 to 15,500 operating hours. The E4 corresponds to the hours leading up to the failure, which occurred before the major maintenance was carried out.

Similar to the previous case, different patterns can be observed in the AE behavior. For E2, the data between the period from 15,700 to 16,200 operating hours were used. Meanwhile, for E4, the data between the period from 16,200 up to the failure were used. The failure occurred on February 18th with 16,837 operating hours and 234 starts.

In this pump, the differences are not as significant as in the previous case. The mean value of AE at the end of the E2 scenario is $7.1 \text{ kW} \pm 5 \text{ kW}$ with a maximum of 25.4 kW. The mean value of AE before the failure, in the E4 scenario, is $7.6 \text{ kW} \pm 6.2 \text{ kW}$ with a maximum of 39.8.

5.3. Application to the GA-115-I secondary pump, in Huelva, in scenarios E1, E2 y E4

The study of the pump was conducted in three of the four scenarios mentioned earlier, specifically, scenarios E1, E2, and E4.

Similar to the previous case, different patterns can be observed in the AE behavior. Training was conducted with data from scenario E1, specifically up to 2,000 operating hours, after the major maintenance. For E2 and E4, data between the period ranging from 2,300 to the failure were used. The failure occurred on March 14, 2016, with 7,605 operating hours.

In this pump, the differences are quite significant. The mean value of AE at the end of scenario E1 is $2.9 \text{ kW} \pm 2.7 \text{ kW}$ with a maximum of 29.7 kW. The mean value of AE before the failure in scenario E4 is $8.4 \text{ kW} \pm 7 \text{ kW}$ with a maximum of 139 kW.

5.4. Application to the GA-115-I secondary pump, in Huelva, in scenarios E1 y E2

The study of the pump was conducted in two of the four scenarios mentioned earlier, specifically, scenarios E1 and E2.

The GA-115-H pump is a case very similar to the previous one (GA-115-I). However, unlike the GA-115-I pump, the GA-115-H pump has not experienced any failures up to the date of the study in 2022.

Unlike the previous pumps, the accumulation of minutes at higher values is less pronounced, with AE values of smaller magnitude than in the previous cases.

Similar to the previous case, different patterns can be observed among them. Training was conducted with data from scenario E1, with approximately 3,500 operating hours. For E2, data were used from around 3,500 to 10,000 operating hours.

In this pump, the differences are not as noticeable. The mean value of AE at the end of scenario E1 is 2.56 kW ± 2.4 kW with a maximum of 60 kW. The mean value of AE during scenario E2 is 6.1 kW ± 5 kW with a maximum of 106 kW.

Table 4 summarizes the results of the Absolute Error (AE) of power in different scenarios and situations of the pumps, providing a comparative view of their performance under various conditions.

Pump	E1 (kW)	E2 (kW)	E4 (kW)	Situation
P-2003-A		5,5 ± 4	12,5 ± 12,9	Failure Post-Overhaul
P-2003-B		7,1 ± 5	7,6 ± 6,2	Failure Pre-Overhaul, in End-of-Life Failure
GA-115-I	2,9 ± 2,7		8,4 ± 7	Failure Pre-Overhaul
GA-115-H	2,6 ± 2,4	6,1 ± 5		No Failure

Table 4. Results of the Absolute Error (AE) of power in different scenarios and situations of the pumps

For faulty pumps, in scenario E2, the probability distribution concentrates around 5.5 kW, with a very sharp-shaped distribution; reaching maximum values of just over 17 kW.

In scenario E4, the probability distribution centers around 12.5 kW, and the distribution is already quite flat, reaching considerably higher values, close to 45 kW (Graph 4).

Graph 4. Probability distribution of the absolute power error (kW), in scenario E2 and just before failure (E4)

The variability, after overhaul (E2) and before failure (E4), along with the highest values of absolute error (kW), suggest potential operational issues. This pattern could serve as an early indicator of failures, emphasizing the importance of continuous monitoring and analysis for anomaly detection.

6. Definition of the classification model based on risk levels (diagnosis)

6.1. Definition and Analysis of Risk Levels

In this section, we commence with the risk analysis for each of the previously identified scenarios.

To enhance the precision of the analysis and to enable a comparative assessment of different equipment across various scenarios, we employ the descriptor **Cumulative Operating Time** at risk level i (TR_i), where i ranges from 0 to 6. Each level of the descriptor corresponds to a distinct risk level for the occurrence of a failure mode. As the accumulation of operating hours increases at higher risk levels (3, 4, 5, and 6), the likelihood of pump failure also escalates. In this instance, it is not feasible to provide a failure probability value associated with each risk level; a statistical study involving a larger number of equipment failures prior to major maintenance would be required (González et al., 2023) (Chelmiah et al., 2022).

Table 5 defines these TR_i descriptors based on the Absolute Error (AE) of power:

TR_i Level	Range AE in kW
TR_0^*	$AE < 15$
TR_1	$15 \leq AE < 20$
TR_2	$20 \leq AE < 25$
TR_3	$25 \leq AE < 30$
TR_4	$30 \leq AE < 35$
TR_5	$35 \leq AE < 40$
TR_6	$45 < AE$

Table 5. Definition of TR_i descriptors.

* For TR_0 , the 15 kW limit is chosen based on observations of the neural network behavior in fault-free pumps, increasing by 5 kW increments according to the average value of such pumps

Furthermore, for each of the use cases, an analysis of the percentage of operating time at each risk level, TR_i , is also conducted.

Graph 5 depicts the evolution of the various TR_i as operating hours accumulate.

Graph 5. Analysis of TR_i levels for pumps P-2003-A (left) and P-2003-B (right).

It is noteworthy that, in pumps experiencing failures (P-2003-A, P-2003-B, GA-115-I), the accumulation of operating time at higher risk levels is more pronounced compared to the pump without failures (GA-115-H) (Li et al., 2022).

Table 6 quantitatively compares the accumulated time at each risk level (TR_i) and the percentage of total operation time for the four pumps.

	TR ₀	TR ₁	TR ₂	TR ₃	TR ₄	TR ₅	TR ₆
PA-2003A	73,39%	11,95%	5,86%	3,16%	0,68%	0,79%	4,17%
PA-2003B	69,22%	18,06%	8,08%	2,84%	1,55%	0,09%	0,17%
GA-115I	84,73%	7,63%	4,36%	2,14%	0,81%	0,25%	0,09%
GA-115H	94,46%	3,65%	0,92%	0,61%	0,30%	0,04%	0,02%

Table 6. Comparative analysis of accumulated time percentages at each risk level TR_i.

The objective of this phase is to define and model a classification algorithm that allows for the establishment of action recommendations based on the state of the failure mode.

A classification algorithm is defined, and training and validation are conducted using the RM class prediction tool.

The following three Class are defined:

- **Class 1:** Corresponds to a failure mode of a piece of equipment that has not yet begun to manifest, thus it can be considered that there is no failure mode detectable through the prediction of the power consumed by the pump. In this case, all operating minutes are accumulated in TR₀, TR₁, and TR₂.
- **Class 2:** Corresponds to a latent failure mode that begins to manifest, detectable by the prediction of consumed power. It is assumed that this rule applies for an accumulation of more than 10 consecutive minutes of operation at risk level TR₃.
- **Class 3:** Corresponds to the final stage of the asset before failure, when it has been confirmed that the equipment exhibits behavior deviating from normal, verified through condition inspections, such as vibration measurements, performance tests, etc.

Table 7 represents the accumulated % of time in each of the following classes: Class 1 (no failure mode), Class 2 (latent failure mode), and Class 3 (existing failure mode).

Classification	C1	C2	C3
PA-2003A	91.20%	3.16%	5.64%
PA-2003B	95.36%	2.84%	1.81%
GA-115I	96.72%	2.14%	1.15%
GA-115H	99.03%	0.61%	0.36%

Table 7. Cumulative percentage of time in each class

In this table, it's evident that for the fault-free pump, the accumulated % of time in high-risk values doesn't exceed 0.5% (GA-115-H; 0.36%). However, for faulty pumps, it already surpasses 1%, with some pumps exceeding 5% (PA-2003-A: 5.64%).

At this point, using RM's Auto Model class prediction tool.

Model	Classification Error	Standard Deviation	Gains	Total Time	Training Time (1,000 Rows)	Scoring Time (1,000 Rows)
Naive Bayes	6.6%	±0.0%	9,384	35 s	4 ms	283 ms
Generalized Linear Model	12.9%	±0.1%	-2,504	1 min 54 s	153 ms	310 ms
Logistic Regression	11.5%	±2.0%	0	1 min 18 s	33 ms	536 ms
Fast Large Margin	11.5%	±0.0%	2	1 hour 5 min 58 s	734 ms	556 ms
Deep Learning	5.4%	±0.0%	8,822	2 min 3 s	256 ms	355 ms
Decision Tree	5.4%	±0.0%	8,710	30 s	9 ms	248 ms
Random Forest	5.5%	±0.1%	2,136	2 min 49 s	42 ms	613 ms
Gradient Boosted Trees	4.4%	±0.0%	2,538	3 min 49 s	209 ms	1 s
Support Vector Machine	10.6%	±0.2%	84	46 min 7 s	492 ms	1 s

Table 8. Results of the comparison of class prediction models.

Table 8 presents a comparison of class prediction models, highlighting that the algorithms with the least error are Gradient Boosted Trees, DL, Decision Tree, and Random Forest. Based on the results, the Decision Tree algorithm is the most practical option. Compared to other algorithms, it stands out for its efficiency in processing time (training, evaluation, and total). It is a simple and easily interpretable model. Regarding classification error, or accuracy, its error rate is quite low (5.4%) and minimal compared to the most accurate algorithm, Gradient Boosted Trees (4.4%).

The results suggest distinctive patterns in pumps experiencing failures; one of these observed patterns is that the pumps operated under more severe conditions before failing, accumulating more operating time at higher risk levels.

7. Recommendations for Operation and Maintenance

The objective of this phase is to define action recommendations based on the state of the failure mode.

Figure 5 represents a proposal for event and action planning based on the equipment's condition, prediction algorithms, and classification algorithms.

Figure 5. Proposed state, events, and actions diagram for a specific failure mode of the pump.

Events can be of two types: detection events (1 and 2) that are automatically activated upon the fulfillment of a rule, and scheduled events (3, 4, and 5) programmed based on the former, which are used for state verification and operation and maintenance actions.

The proposed sequence of events is as follows.

1. Prior to the occurrence of the first event, the pump is operating normally, with only the power prediction algorithm in use.
2. Event 1 occurs, and the neural network detects, for the first time, a prediction error greater than 25 kW. At this moment, the following analyses are initiated:
 - a. Accumulated minutes counter at risk level TR3 ($25 \text{ kW} \leq \text{AE} < 30 \text{ kW}$).
 - b. Diagnosis by the classification algorithm of the pump's state.
3. Event 2 occurs, and the automatic classification-based diagnosis predicts that the pump's failure mode is state 2, with a probability greater than 60% that this is the case. The following actions are initiated at this event:
 - a. The pump is set to a non-priority startup state.
 - b. Event 3 for vibration diagnosis is scheduled.
 - c. The failure mode state transitions to a medium risk level.
4. Execution of Event 3, vibration diagnosis. At this moment, two outcomes are possible: either it is verified that the pump has high vibrations, associated with a particular failure mode, or the pump shows no anomalies in the vibration analysis. If the former occurs, Event 4 is planned, and the pump's state transitions to a high-risk level. If, on the contrary, the pump does not exhibit high vibrations, the pump remains at the medium risk level and is put under monitoring.
5. Execution of Event 4 involves diagnosing the pump through inspection and examination. If a failure mode is confirmed in the pump, maintenance intervention or replacement is scheduled depending on the state .
6. Execution of Event 5 involves maintenance intervention based on condition, preventing the onset of the failure mode. Subsequently, a Corrective Action Request (CAR) is carried out for the identified failure mode.

If necessary, and based on the results of the previous analysis, it is advisable to retrain the automatic classification-based diagnosis for the failure modes that have occurred. This helps to achieve a more precise adjustment of the diagnosis.

8. Conclusions

The paper focuses on the early identification of anomalies (prognosis) and the classification of failure modes in secondary pumps (diagnosis).

The prognosis part aids in failure prevention, enabling actions to be taken prior to failure; in maintenance planning, either reducing or increasing the frequency of scheduled maintenance to mitigate the risk of failure; and enhancing safety to prevent accidents and injuries by isolating the pump if necessary.

The identification of the occurring failure mode or diagnosis of the failure mode assists technicians in determining the causes of the failure and making decisions about the repair or replacement of the equipment or its parts; identifying the most probable failure modes; and focusing on the failure modes that require priority attention.

This document presents an analysis method based on the condition state of the secondary pumps, with four different scenarios through which a pump can pass or has passed, for prognosis. It also defines risk levels based on AE, in which the accumulated times at each level are measured, for the diagnosis of failure modes.

Nine ML algorithms were compared for prediction or prognosis, and another nine for classification or diagnosis, with the aim of ensuring the selection of the best model depending on the balance between accuracy, efficiency in training and evaluation time, and above all, the complexity of the problem.

For prediction, a Neural Network algorithm (RNN-7-5-1) was chosen and validated with four pumps, three of which experienced failures in different scenarios and one without a failure. It is clearly observed that in all pumps during scenarios E1/E2, they exhibit behavior that is completely different than before the failure, in scenarios E3/E4. In scenarios E3/E4, more minutes accumulate in higher absolute error values. Meanwhile, in the pump without failures, the AE trend does not change.

For the classification model, three stages were defined: Stage 1, when the failure mode has not yet begun to manifest, corresponding to risk levels TR0, TR1, and TR2; Stage 2, where the failure mode begins to manifest, accumulating more than 10 consecutive minutes at risk level TR3; and Stage 3, which corresponds to before the failure, where the pump's behavior deviates from its normal behavior and more times accumulate at risk levels TR4, TR5, and TR6. Based on this classification, the Decision Tree algorithm was chosen, where it is observed that for the three pumps that experienced failures, the prediction of their stage was 3, with a greater accumulation of time at risk levels TR4, TR5, and TR6, at approximately 5%; whereas for the pump without failure, the accumulation of times at risk levels TR4, TR5, and TR6 was approximately 1%, demonstrating the importance of diagnostic methods in maintenance management.

Lastly, maintenance recommendations are provided based on the analyses conducted.

It is concluded that the application of ML to identify malfunction patterns in cryogenic pumps is a significant advancement for these types of hard-to-access assets. With the technology used so far and the maintenance plans, there was still uncertainty, leading to either over-maintenance or under-maintenance, depending on the strategies.

9. Implications for Future Studies

It is necessary to extend the study to encompass the entire pump fleet at Enagás to demonstrate the scalability of the model and validate it across different operational scenarios. Moreover, as data collection expands, it will be essential to enhance and refine the models through retraining with new data, thereby optimizing them and enabling comparisons with new models.

Additionally, a relevant analysis would be to investigate less frequent failure scenarios, specifically identifying the “rarest” failures using anomaly detection techniques or other existing methods. Furthermore, it is crucial to assess the economic impact to analyze the costs associated with corrective actions versus those incurred with predictive models. This evaluation would include

assessing the reduction in downtime and the increase in equipment lifespan, as well as optimizing maintenance plans to balance maintenance frequency and reduce the risk of failure.

The comparison between the most advanced DL models and traditional methods for predictive maintenance has demonstrated that DL models are more effective. Incorporating these alternative approaches could facilitate a broader discussion of the findings and enhance the overall effectiveness of the predictive maintenance framework.

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3rd OF JULY 2024 DRAFT PROGRAM

09.00 10.00	WELCOME - OPENING ADRESSES			
10.00 10.45	PLENARY SESSION ISABEL PARDO DE VERA. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE: PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO			
10.45 11.15	COFFEE BREAK			
11.15 12.45	RAIL SESSION Digitalization in manufacturing and O&M of railway rolling stock	CIBERSECURITY SESSION Decentralized cybersecurity of critical engineering assets	Strategy & Planning	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 1
12.45 14.15	LUNCH			
14.15 15.00	PLENARY SESSION CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH, COPPERLEAF. OPTIMISED ASSET INVESTMENT PLANNING WITH COPPERLEAF - MAKING THE RIGHT DECISIONS AT THE RIGHT TIME TO MAXIMISE VALUE AND MEET STRATEGIC GOALS			
15.00 16.30	RAIL SESSION Digital Transformation in Rail Infrastructure	DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT SESSION Digitalization and Risk Management of Critical Engineering Assets	Life Cycle Management 1	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 2
16.30 17.00	COFFEE BREAK			
17.00 18.30	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	HYDROGEN SESSION Technical and Energetic Challenges in the Transition from Natural gas to Hydrogen	Life Cycle Management 2	SPECIAL SESSION Digital IAMS for integral LCM
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL			

4th OF JULY 2024 DRAFT PROGRAM

09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION ABEL GOMES. APPLUS. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE LA INFRAESTRUCTURA			
09.45 10.30	PLENARY SESSION NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUAEPAL.			
10.30 11.00	COFFEE BREAK			
11.00 12.30	APMI-AEM SESSION Maintenance and Asset Management. Future and Trends in the Iberian Region	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION BIOCHAR Applications and Circular Economy	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 1	WORKSHOP The Copperleaf optimization game
12.30 14.00	LUNCH			
14.00 14.45	PLENARY SESSION. TIAGO FERNANDES, ALFONSO LACERDA. EVORA GOLD PARTNER SAP. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE- THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL WORLD.			
14.45 16.15	APMI-AEM SESSION People in Maintenance and Asset management in the Iberian Region	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Improving asset management in local governments	Management Systems and Standards 1	Sustainability 1
16.15 16.45	COFFEE BREAK			
16.45 18.15	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Building sustainable communities with asset management	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 2	Management Systems and Standards 2
20.00	GALA DINNER			

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5th OF JULY 2024 DRAFT PROGRAM

09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION. JOE AMADI-ECHENDU , DAVID MCKEON,, EDMEA ADELL, ALAN WILSON. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS .			
09.45 11.15	CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SESSION The role of asset management in the resilience of critical infrastructure	ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETITION	Sustainability 2	Risk & Reliability
11.15 11.45	COFFEE BREAK			
11.45 13.15	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION Intelligent Asset Management : People, Processes and Technology as enablers for ISO 55001 Certification	Data Asset and Digital Transformation	Sustainability 3	People & Competence
13.15 14.00	CLOSING CEREMONY			
14.00	LUNCH			

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09.00 AUDITORIUM I	WELCOME - OPENING ADRESSES
	<i>Hugo Espírito Santo. Secretary of State for Infrastructure Rogério Colaço. Dean of Instituto Superior Técnico- UL Isabel Pardo de Vera. Ex-Secretary of State for Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda. Ex-Chairwoman of ADIF Carlos Manuel Martins. Chair of the Board of Directors of EPAL Isabel Rodríguez Ramos. Director of Construction Knowledge Area Mediterranean Region at Applus</i>
10.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 44. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO. ISABEL PARDO DE VERA.
10.45	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY CAF
11.15 AUDITORIUM I	RAIL SESSION. ID 119. DIGITALIZATION IN MANUFACTURING AND O&M OF RAILWAY ROLLING STOCK.
	<i>Chair: Luis Andrade Ferreira. Centro de Competências Ferroviário Javier de la Cruz, CAF José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Alexandra Prates. CP Metropolitano de Lisboa</i>
11.15 AUDITORIUM III	CYBERSECURITY SESSION. ID 58. NAORIS PROTOCOL: WORLD'S FIRST DECENTRALIZED CYBERSECURITY MESH ARCHITECTURE. DAVID CARVALHO
	ID 116. BRIDGING THE GAP: WEB 3.0 AND CYBER-PHYSICAL INTEGRATION IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT
	<i>Chair: João Santos. Naoris David Carvalho. Naoris Miguel Oliveira. University of Aveiro Luis Ramalhão Santos. OET Jorge Liça. OE Carlos Ribeiro. Ex Director CSI</i>
11.15 ROOM 2	STRATEGY & PLANNING. CHAIR JAIME GABRIEL SILVA.
ID 23	PUBLIC CAPITAL STOCK UNVEILED: EXAMINING INVESTMENT TRENDS AND THE CONDITION OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN PORTUGAL. JOÃO VIEIRA
ID 28	ASSET MANAGEMENT: QUAL O VOLUME DE DADOS É NECESSARIO PARA A TOMADA DE DECISÃO DE ALTO VALOR AGREGADO?. CELSO DE AZEVEDO
ID 38	COMO MELHORAR O PLANO DE INVESTIMENTOS DE UMA ORGANIZAÇÃO DE CAPITAL INTENSIVO. MARIANA CASALTA

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ID 84	PLANEJAMENTO ESTRATÉGICO DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS EM EMPRESAS DE SANEAMENTO – ESTUDO DE CASO EMBASA. ALISSON BRANDÃO
ID 108	ALIGNING AND ENGAGING LEADERSHIP AND TEAMS TOWARDS COMMON OBJECTIVES: THE ROLE OF CULTURAL SAMP IN ASSET MANAGEMENT. TICO MONTEIRO
ID 111	FROM DATA TO DECISIONS: EMPOWERING PIPELINE OPERATORS WITH ACTIONABLE INSIGHTS. ANA SILVA
11.15 ROOM 5	PERFORMANCE AND CONDITION OF PHYSICAL ASSETS. SESSION 1. CHAIR ÁLVARO RODRÍGUEZ PRIETO
ID 9	PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT IN RETAIL WATER UTILITIES: GUIDING ASSET MANAGEMENT BY IDENTIFYING PEERS AND TARGETS. HERMILIO VILARINHO
ID 12	ASSESSMENT OF THE TECHNICAL AND FUNCTIONAL PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC BUILDINGS. FILIPA SALVADO
ID 18	TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF ALTERNATIVE REFRIGERANTS WITH LOWER GWP FOR THE RETROFIT OF HEAT PUMPS WITH R410A. PEDRO BARANDIER
ID 48	ENERGETIC AND ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE HVAC TEMPERATURE SETPOINT ADJUSTMENT IN COMMERCIAL AND SERVICE BUILDINGS. PEDRO BARANDIER
ID 62	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS E A OTIMIZAÇÃO DA EFICIÊNCIA EM LABORATÓRIOS DE ENSAIOS DE MATERIAIS. EDUARDO GANILHO
ID 92	FROM VIDEO ACQUISITION TO EXPERIMENTAL MODAL ANALYSIS. TIAGO SILVA
12.45	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
14.15 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 4. OPTIMISED ASSET INVESTMENT PLANNING WITH COPPERLEAF - MAKING THE RIGHT DECISION AT THE RIGHT TIME TO MAXIMISE VALUE AND MEET STRATEGIC GOALS. CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH.
15.00 AUDITORIUM I	RAIL SESSION. ID 120. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN RAIL INFRASTRUCTURE.
	<i>Chair: Esther Mateo Rodríguez. ADIF Dolores Sanz. IDOM Fernando Vara. ACCIONA Valentí Fontseré. COMSA Montserrat Álvarez. Ineco Paulo Duarte. PFP Rui Coutinho. Infraestruturas de Portugal</i>

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15.00 AUDITORIUM III	DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT SESSION. ID 132. EQS: ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY. HOW DIGITALIZATION SERVES AS A TRANSFORMATIVE TOOL . HUGO BRANQUINHO
	ID 133. DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT OF CRITICAL ENGINEERING ASSETS. AN ISO 55000-BASED DIGITAL APPROACH TO MONITOR, EVALUATE, AND IMPROVE DECISION PROCESSES FOR ASSET-INTENSIVE INDUSTRIES.
	Chair. Cláudia Rocha. EQS Luís Nicolau. Aguas do Norte Nuno Joaquim.Repsol Hugo Branquinho. EQS Duarte Dias . INESCTEC
15.00 ROOM 2	LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT. SESSION 1. CHAIR MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO.
ID 14	RESILIENCE AND LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT OF CRITICAL URBAN ASSET SYSTEMS IN FACE OF EMERGING THREATS. SEYED REZVANI
ID 22	VARIAÇÃO DO CUSTO ANUAL EQUIVALENTE AO LONGO DO CICLO DE VIDA DE EDIFÍCIOS PÚBLICOS. FILIPA SALVADO
ID 29	APPLICATION OF ASSET INVESTMENT PLANNING TOOL IN A PORTFOLIO OF PHYSICAL ASSETS. MARIA PINHEIRO
ID 36	A MODULAR & STREAMLINED APPROACH FOR MODELLING ASSET HEALTH AND RISK IN INFRASTRUCTURE ASSETS BASED ON FMECA METHODOLOGY. ZENA TULEMAT
ID 42	EVOLUÇÃO, INOVAÇÃO E APLICAÇÃO DE SISTEMAS DE CONSTRUÇÃO PRÉ-FABRICADA EM EDIFÍCIOS. MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO SILVA
ID 43	ANÁLISIS DE LOS COSTES DE INVERSIÓN Y OPERATIVOS EN EL CICLO DE VIDA DEL MATERIAL RODANTE FERROVIARIO: IMPLICACIONES PARA LOS ACTORES CLAVE Y ESTRATEGIAS DE GESTIÓN. JUAN MANUEL RAMÍREZ BUENO
15.00 ROOM 5	PERFORMANCE AND CONDITION OF PHYSICAL ASSETS. SESSION 2. CHAIR CARLOS PARRA.
ID 68	ASSET PERFORMANCE REPORTING AS A KEY ELEMENT IN A ROAD AND RAIL ASSET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM. JOÃO MORGADO
ID 76	OPERATIONAL DAMAGE DETECTION ON BRIDGES: UNVEILING THE IMPACT OF THE TRAINING DATASET. JORGE VIEIRA
ID 79	ESTUDIO DE CAUSAS Y SOLUCIONES PARA LA GESTIÓN DE PUENTES EN ECUADOR. ESTEFANÍA CERVANTES

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ID 86	SATELLITE-BASED DISPLACEMENT MONITORING FOR ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE MAINTENANCE AND SAFETY. NUNO DURO
ID 91	TECNOLOGIA DE AMPLIFICAÇÃO DE MOVIMENTO NO ÂMBITO DA MANUTENÇÃO PREDITIVA (MOTION AMPLIFICATION). ANTONIO ROQUE
16.30	COFFEE BREAK
17.00 AUDITORIUM I	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR NUNO ALMEIDA
ID 129	LA BUENA VIDA DE LAS INFRAESTRUCTURAS. SERGIO VÁZQUEZ TORRÓN. INECO
ID 126	DIGITALIZACIÓN Y GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. BEGOÑA MARTÍN Y JOÃO DIONISIO. COMSA
ID 131	PROJETO TRANSVERSAL DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS PARA O MATERIAL CIRCULANTE E OFICINAS FERROVIÁRIAS - UMA ABORDAGEM PRÁTICA PARA A MELHORIA DOS PROCESSOS E DA PRODUTIVIDADE. SILVIA FERREIRA Y MIGUEL RODRIGUES. CP
17.00 AUDITORIUM III	HYDROGEN SESSION. ID 99. TECHNICAL AND ENERGETIC CHALLENGES IN THE TRANSITION FROM NATURAL GAS TO HYDROGEN. ENAGAS
	Chair: Javier Serra. Enagas
17.00 ROOM 2	LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT. SESSION 2. ESTEFANÍA CERVANTES.
ID 51	ON-LINE CONDITION MONITORING OF ELECTRIC MOTOR DRIVES BASED ON ELECTRICAL ANALYSIS – SUCCESS CASE STUDIES IN INDUSTRY. JORGE ESTIMA
ID 55	POTENTIAL IMPACTS OF IMPLEMENTING CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES IN THE NIGERIAN FOREST PRODUCTS INDUSTRY: A SOCIAL LIFECYCLE ANALYSIS APPROACH. ISRAEL DUNMADE
ID 59	APLICACIÓN DE AUDITORÍA DE MANTENIMIENTO Y MODELO DE GESTIÓN DE MANTENIMIENTO A EMPRESA MANUFACTURERA DE PRODUCTOS COSMÉTICOS. CARLOS PARRA
ID 61	FACTORES DE SUCESSO E BLOQUEIO NO PLANEAMENTO E GESTÃO DAS INFRAESTRUTURAS URBANAS DE SUBSOLO. ANDRÉ SALVADOR
ID 104	AUDITORIA TÉCNICA NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS INDUSTRIAIS: UMA ABORDAGEM SUSTENTÁVEL NA PERSPETIVA DA OTIMIZAÇÃO DO CICLO DE VIDA ÚTIL. CLÁUDIA ROCHA

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17.00 ROOM 5	SPECIAL SESSION. DIGITAL INTELLIGENT ASSET MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS (IAMS) FOR INTEGRAL ASSET LIFECYCLE MANAGEMENT. CHAIR ADOLFO CRESPO DEL CASTILLO.
ID 21	EXPLORING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT'S EFFECT ON LIFE CYCLE COSTS WITH DIGITALIZATION'S SUPPORT. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ-PRIDA
ID 24	EARLY FAILURE DETECTION IN SECONDARY CRYOGENIC PUMPS THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY 4.0. SONIA LIÑAN
ID 45	DYNAMIC FLEET MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT: INTEGRATING PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE AND PREDICTIVE CBM WITH OPERATION SCHEDULING. ADOLFO CRESPO DEL CASTILLO
ID 46	FRAMEWORK FOR ASSET DIGITALIZATION: A HOLISTIC APPROACH FOR ENHANCED MANAGEMENT AND RELIABILITY IN THE DIGITAL ERA. EDUARDO CANDÓN
ID 47	STRATEGIC INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE: TRANSFORMING ASSET MANAGEMENT ACROSS THE LIFECYCLE FOR INFORMED DECISION-MAKING. ADOLFO CRESPO MÁRQUEZ
ID 80	DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT. GFM&AM'S PROJECT 25DX INSIGHTS. ADOLFO CRESPO MÁRQUEZ
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL OCEANÁRIO

4th of July Draft Programme

09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 123. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE INFRAESTRUCTURAS. ABEL GOMES. APPLUS.
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 134. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUA. NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL.
10.30	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY AYESA
11.00 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 121 MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT: FUTURE AND TRENDS IN THE IBERO-AMERICAN SPACE <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez Claudio Rodríguez. AEM Diogo Brito. APMI Marcela Scalco. ABRAMAN</i>
	ID 122. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Pedro Conceição (SONAE ARAUCO) Hugo Lebre (INFRASPEAK) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM III	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION. ID 95: BIOCHAR APPLICATIONS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY. ATIV <i>Chair: Cátia Neves. ATIV - Mota ENGIL</i>
11.00 ROOM 2	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 1. ANTONIO GUILLÉN LÓPEZ.
ID 11	THE IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE ASSET MAINTENANCE IN TELECOMS DOMAIN IN EMERGING MARKETS. CHARLES OKEYIA
ID 13	CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY AND OVERCOMING THE DIGITALIZATION DEFICIT OF THE AECO INDUSTRY. SEYED REZVAN
ID 89	IMPLANTAÇÃO DE SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA EMBASA: INTEGRAÇÃO DE SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO. RINALDO CAMURUGY
ID 33	MODELAÇÃO PARAMÉTRICA DE ANOMALIAS EM TÚNEIS FERROVIÁRIOS. ANA ROCHA
ID 106	A VALUE-BASED DECISION-MAKING PROCESS FOR DIGITAL TWINNING OPPORTUNITIES IN RAIL AND ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET MANAGEMENT. JOÃO VIEIRA

ID 3	DIGITALIZATION STRATEGY FOR ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY'S NET-ZERO TRANSITION. <i>ÁLVARO RODRÍGUEZ PRIETO</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM II	WORKSHOP. ID 5. THE COPPERLEAF OPTIMIZATION GAME. CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH.
12.30	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
14.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 130. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE – THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN A DIGITAL WORLD. TIAGO FERNANDES, SAP & ALFONSO LACERDA, EVORA.
14.45 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 124. PEOPLE IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION .
	<i>Chair: Daniel Gaspar José Luis Bernal. MASA Álvaro Rodríguez Prieto. UNED Paulo Peixoto (ATEC) Mário Aguiam (ISQ)</i>
14.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 96. IMPROVING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN LOCAL GOVERNMENTS. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
14.45 ROOM 2	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 1. CHAIR RITA BRITO.
ID 19	SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA MANUTENÇÃO DE PAVIMENTOS RODOVIÁRIOS. <i>JOSÉ VAZ</i>
ID 27	LOS SISTEMAS DE GETIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE CARRETERAS COMO HERRAMIENTAS PARA LA OPTIMIZACIÓN DE LOS PRESUPUESTOS DE CONSERVACIÓN. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 83	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS APLICADA EMPRESAS DE SANEAMENTO: IMPLANTAÇÃO DE MODELO NA EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO (EMBASA). <i>ALISSON BRANDÃO</i>
ID 77	NEW VALUE PERSPECTIVE FOR SOCIAL PRICELESS ASSETS THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS. <i>JOAQUÍN ORDIERES-MERÉ</i>
ID 78	DESAFIOS ATUAIS DA E-REDES NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS TÉCNICOS. <i>MIGUEL FREITAS</i>
14.45 ROOM 5	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 1. CHAIR: ANA SILVA.
ID 56	AVALIAÇÃO EX-ANTE DA PRODUÇÃO DE MISTURAS BETUMINOSAS CONSIDERANDO TRÊS CENÁRIOS DE PRODUÇÃO ALTERNATIVOS. <i>ANA ROCHA</i>

ID 71	THE SYNERGY BETWEEN LEAN PHILOSOPHY AND VALUE ENGINEERING FOR NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 72	SOLUÇÃO CONJUGADA DE CONSTRUÇÃO TRADICIONAL E TECNOLOGIA MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS SUSTENTÁVEIS EM CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTES</i>
ID 75	"BOTICAR" PROJECT – THE FIRST STEPS TOWARDS DECARBONISATION IN PORTUGAL
ID 90	IMPLANTAÇÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NO SISTEMA DE ABASTECIMENTO DE ÁGUA E ESGOTAMENTO SANITÁRIO DE BARRA DE POJUCA NA EMBASA – EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO. <i>RINALDO CAMURUGY</i>
16.15	COFFEE BREAK
16.45 AUDITORIUM I	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR JOAQUÍN ORDIERES
	GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. TALGO
ID 128	IMPORTANCIA DEL FACTOR HUMANO EN LA APLICACIÓN DE LA INGENIERÍA DEL MANTENIMIENTO EN LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS. <i>JOSÉ LUIS BERNAL. MASA</i>
ID 115	UN ENFOQUE UNIFICADO DE LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS MEDIANTE SAP Y BIM EN AT/MT/BT ELÉCTRICA. <i>IGNACIO MORATALLA AGUIRRE. AYESA</i>
16.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 97. BUILDING SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITIES WITH ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
16.45 ROOM 2	DATA ASSETS & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 2. CHAIR: VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA.
ID 15	INDUSTRIAL IOT AND 3D DIGITAL TWIN FOR REAL TIME-EVERGREENING OF ENGINEERING ASSETS SUBJECTED TO CORROSION UNDER INSULATION. <i>ALVARO RODRÍGUEZ-PRIETO</i>
ID 26	UNA EFICAZ GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE REDES DE CARRETERAS A PARTIR DE GEMELOS DIGITALES. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 70	OVERVIEW OF THE USE OF DATA ASSETS IN THE CONTEXT OF PORTUGUESE COMPANIES: COMPARISON BETWEEN SMES AND LARGE COMPANIES. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 73	MODIFICAÇÃO DO MÉTODO DELPHI PARA APLICAÇÃO NUM QUESTIONÁRIO SOBRE A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>SAMUEL MESSIAS</i>
ID 103	NDE & SENSING SOLUTIONS FOR PIPELINE STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING. <i>GABRIEL DINIS</i>
ID 112	DIGITALIZING BUILDING MAINTENANCE: BIM-POWERED ASSET MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS. <i>ANA SILVA</i>

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16.45 ROOM 5	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 2. FILIPA SALVADO.
ID 16	COLLECTIVE USE BUILDINGS ASSET MANAGEMENT BASED ON TECHNICAL AND ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENTS. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO</i>
ID 35	IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS OF AN ISO 55001 CERTIFIED ASSET MANAGEMENT MODEL IN THE NATURAL GAS INDUSTRY. <i>JAVIER SERRA</i>
ID 41	IMPLEMENTACIÓN DE UN PLAN DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS SEGÚN LA NORMA ISO 55001 EN LA CENTRAL DE GENERACIÓN ELÉCTRICA COLMITO.
ID 63	A EVOLUÇÃO E PERSPETIVAS DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS: UM MODELO ABRANGENTE E INTEGRADO DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS INDUSTRIAIS. <i>JOAQUIM CABRAL MARTINS</i>
ID 82	CERTIFICAÇÃO ISO 55001 NA E-REDES – UMA AVALIAÇÃO APÓS DOIS ANOS. <i>CRISTINA CARVALHO</i>
ID 110	IMPORTÂNCIA DO ALINHAMENTO DAS FUNÇÕES ORGANIZACIONAIS E DA ESTRUTURAÇÃO DOS ATIVOS NA TOMADA DE DECISÃO SOBRE INVESTIMENTOS NO SETOR DA ÁGUA. <i>JAIME GABRIEL SILVA</i>
20.00	GALA DINNER KAIS RESTAURANTE

5th of July Draft Programme

09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION ID 113. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS.
	Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez David Mckewon. Vicepresidente honorario del Instituto de Gestión de Activos Joe Amadi Echendu. Presidente de la Junta Directiva de la Sociedad Internacional de Gestión de Activos de Ingeniería Edmea Adell. Presidente de IFRAMI y miembro de ISO/TC 251 Asset Management Alan Wilson. Representante del Comité de Gestión de Activos de la Federación Europea de Sociedades Nacionales de Mantenimiento
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SESSION. ID 135. THE ROLE OF ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE RESILIENCE OF CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE. EPAL
	Chair: Ana Margarida Luís. AdP Valor Miguel Freitas. E-REDES Vanessa Martins. EPAL Javier Serra. ENAGÁS Infraestructuras de Portugal
09.45 AUDITORIUM III	ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETITION. CHAIR EDUARDO LEITE
ID 8	EUROPEAN ACTION TOWARDS MORE ENTREPRENEURIAL AND INNOVATIVE UNIVERSITIES. <i>NUNO ALMEIDA</i>
ID 74	ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: FAILURE PREVENTION AS A PILLAR FOR SUCESS. <i>EDUARDO LEITE</i>
ID 20	NETOBRA. A TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT FOR URBAN RESILIENCE IN THE AECO SECTOR. <i>SEYED REZVANI</i>
ID 117	SPOTLITE. RISK MONITORING FROM SPACE. <i>NUNO DURO</i>
ID 127	DIPROTOS. SISTEMA DE MONITORIZAÇÃO E VIGILÂNCIA DOS ATIVOS: PARQUES PÚBLICOS INFANTIS E DE LAZER. <i>ANTÓNIO ROQUE</i>
ID 94	BCIRCLE. PROJECTO "BOTICHAR". UMA UNIDADE DE PRODUÇÃO EFICIENTE E ESCALÁVEL. <i>DIEGO ARÁN</i>
ID 102	AECYCLE. SUSTAINABLE AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 109	CASADOMO. HABITAÇÃO INOVADORA E SUSTENTÁVEL EM SUPERDOBE MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS DA CIDADE DA PRAIA - CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTÉS</i>
09.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 2. CHAIR ANA LUÍSA CABRITA
ID 114	SUSTAINABILITY AND OTHER OUTCOMES - THE VALUE OF A STRATEGIC ASSET MANAGEMENT APPROACH. <i>DAVID MCKEOWN</i>

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ID 31	A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN EUROPE TO MEASURE THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT POLICIES, INDUSTRY ON PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY. <i>KHULOUD KALTHOUM</i>
ID 17	PROTECTING AND REALIZING VALUE FROM POLLINATION ASSETS: BEEKEEPING OR ASSET MANAGEMENT APPLIED TO NATURAL ASSETS?. <i>AZUCENA MARQUES</i>
ID 52	CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN INDUSTRY 5.0 – A RESEARCH AGENDA
ID 54	A STUDY ON THE PERCEPTION AND AWARENESS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES BY MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN SANGO-OTA REGION, OGUN STATE NIGERIA. <i>ISRAEL DUNMADE</i>
ID 107	HARNESSING THE POWER OF BIOMIMICRY FOR SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION IN PRODUCT DESIGN AND INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT. <i>ARUNA M</i>
09.45 ROOM 5	RISK & RELIABILITY. CHAIR ANTONIO SÁNCHEZ.
ID 6	DATA MODEL TO DIGITIZATION OF CRITICALITY ANALYSIS IN RAILWAY SYSTEMS. <i>ÁNGEL MENA</i>
ID 1	APLICACIÓN DEL MODELO DE GESTIÓN DE MANTENIMIENTO (MGM) ALINEADO A UN PROCESO INTEGRAL DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS.CASO DE ESTUDIO: SINEA PERÚ, EMPRESA LÍDER EN LATINOAMÉRICA DEL SECTOR DE PRODUCCIÓN ENVASES RECICLADOS PARA BEBIDAS COMERCIALES (PET). <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 7	MATRIZ DE CRITICIDAD CUALITATIVA DE RIESGO (MCCR) APLICADA EN UNA LÍNEA DE PRODUCCIÓN DE ENVASES BIODEGRADABLES, <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 30	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VISÃO GERAL DA ESTRUTURA E FUNCIONAMENTO. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
ID 25	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VALIDAÇÃO COM BASE EM DADOS REAIS. <i>JOÃO VINAGRE AMADO</i>
11.15	COFFEE BREAK
11.45 AUDITORIUM I	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION. ID 125. INTELLIGENT ASSET MANAGEMENT : PEOPLE , PROCESSES AND TECHNOLOGY AS ENABLERS FOR ISO 55001 CERTIFICATION. EVORA/SAP
	<i>Chair: Patrícia Franganito (Bureau Veritas) Tiago Fernandes (SAP EMEA) João Moura (Ernst & Young) Paula Branco (Metro do Porto) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>

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11.45 AUDITORIUM III	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 3. CHAIR HUGO PATRÍCIO.
ID 37	GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIER-BASED APPROACH ON WASTEWATER NETWORK AGE PREDICTION FOR CRITICAL ASSETS IDENTIFICATION. <i>RICARDO FERREIRA</i>
ID 49	DIGITALIZAÇÃO E ANÁLISE FUNCIONAL INTEGRADA (AFI) NO PROCESSO DE TOMADA DE DECISÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>HUGO BRANQUINHO</i>
ID 50	INFODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE DETECTION OF BRIDGES. <i>JORGE ALEXANDRE VIEIRA</i>
ID 57	MONITOREO DE LA SALUD ESTRUCTURAL MEDIANTE REALIDAD AUMENTADA Y VIRTUAL: UNA REVISIÓN INTEGRAL. <i>MATÍAS VALENZUELA</i>
ID 66	AVALIAÇÃO METODOLÓGICA DA APLICABILIDADE DA MONITORIZAÇÃO POR SATÉLITE NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS RODOFERROVIÁRIOS. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
11.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 3. CHAIR JOSÉ CAMPOS E MATOS.
ID 32	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS DE ÁGUAS PLUVIAIS EM MEIO URBANO EM PORTUGAL – DESAFIOS PARA O SETOR. <i>RITA SALGADO BRITO</i>
ID 39	REALITY CAPTURE AND MODELLING FOR DIGITAL WATER MANAGEMENT: CASE STUDY OF WATER INFRASTRUCTURE ASSETS IN BRAZIL. <i>WAGNER CARVALHO</i>
ID 81	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA AVALIAÇÃO DA QUALIDADE NA GESTÃO E OTIMIZAÇÃO DE ATIVOS FOTOVOLTAICOS. <i>TERESA CANELAS</i>
ID 93	PATHWAYS TOWARDS NET-ZERO: MARKET DATA INSIGHTS ON PORTUGUESE REAL ESTATE ENERGY PERFORMANCE
ID 100	TRANSIÇÃO DIGITAL E INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA NO SETOR AECO - ESTRATÉGIAS INTEGRADAS PARA UM FUTURO SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 105	COMO TORNAR UM AMS – ASSET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OPERACIONAL E SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>EDMEA ADELL</i>
11.45 ROOM 5	PEOPLE AND COMPETENCE. CHAIR TICO MONTEIRO
ID 10	INNOVATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT SKILLS TOWARDS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO SILVA</i>
ID 53	PROFICIÊNCIA DIGITAL DE ESTUDANTES DE ENGENHARIA: DESAFIOS E OPORTUNIDADES NO CENÁRIO EUROPEU. <i>CELIA DO CARMO LEANDRO</i>

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ID 60	FORTALECENDO A RESILIÊNCIA CLIMÁTICA EM SÃO TOMÉ E PRÍNCIPE: CAPACITAÇÃO DE JORNALISTAS PARA UMA COMUNICAÇÃO EFICAZ.
ID 87	PROPUESTA DE METODOLOGÍA DE GESTIÓN DEL CAMBIO COMO COMPLEMENTO AL MARCO DE REFERENCIA PARA UNA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS INTANGIBLES Y CONOCIMIENTO. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA
ID 118	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA FORMAÇÃO PARA UM MELHOR DESEMPENHO NOS MÉTODOS E PLANEAMENTO DA MANUTENÇÃO DE ATIVOS. DÉRCIO DIAS
ID 2	CRITICAL ASSETS AND VALUE NETWORKS IN RESILIENT INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN THE EU OUTERMOST REGIONS. EDUARDO LEITE
13.15 AUDITORIUM I	CLOSING CEREMONY BEST PAPER DIGITALIZATION BEST PAPER SUSTAINABILITY ENTERPREUNERSHIP COMPETITION LIFETIME ACHIEVEMENT AWARD
13.45	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
